

MINIMIZING VOLATILE-INDUCED SURFACE POROSITY IN RTM VIA MATERIAL AND PROCESS OPTIMIZATION

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Keywords: Porosity, Processing, Cure kinetics

ABSTRACT

We describe RTM manufacturing challenges and solutions using a benzoxazine/epoxy blended resin, in which the complex composition and in-process behavior can cause volatile-induced surface porosity. We investigate material and process modifications that tailor the resin cure kinetics to reduce or eliminate surface defects. The effect of catalyst loading on volatile release is clarified through thermal characterization tests (DSC, TGA, & RDA), and the formation of surface porosity under various cure cycles is demonstrated using a lab-scale RTM tool featuring a glass tool-plate that allows *in situ* observations of in-mold phenomena. The results show, first, that surface porosity is primarily a consequence of rapid curing in the presence of thermal gradients, and second, that surface porosity can be almost entirely eliminated by using a high-catalyst formulation with a 2-stage cure cycle. Overall, the study explains the mechanism behind volatile-induced surface porosity, and shows that effective mitigation strategies can be developed by clarifying the underlying physical phenomena and translating these insights into science-based modifications of the material and process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is a popular composite manufacturing technique for geometrically complex small to medium-sized parts that require low microstructural defect levels and excellent surface finish [1]. Voids – the most common defect encountered in RTM parts – are often a result of air trapped within the mold cavity during injection [2–4]. However, voids can also form after injection, during the curing phase of processing, due to volatiles released by the resin [5]. The positive hydrostatic pressure used during RTM can initially suppress volatile release [6], but chemical cure shrinkage due to polymerization eventually (and inevitably) causes the pressure to drop and tensile stresses to develop in the mold cavity [7]. If the resin viscosity is still low at this time, void nucleation and growth can occur.

1.1 Volatile-induced surface porosity

The resin used in this study is a blended formulation that includes benzoxazine and epoxy components, which exhibits increased volatility compared to most aerospace epoxies. Previous work by the authors has shown that a hydrostatic pressure of ~200 kPa is sufficient to suppress volatile release [8,9]. This pressure level is well within the limits of most RTM tools, but the challenge lies in maintaining mold cavity pressure in the presence of chemical cure shrinkage due to polymerization.

Because the internal volume of a rigid RTM tool is effectively constant, density changes in the resin can cause significant variations in cavity pressure. Prior to gelation, a constant-pressure supply at the inlet allows post-injection resin flow to occur. Additional resin can enter the cavity to compensate for cure shrinkage, and resin can also back-flow through the inlet to maintain pressure equilibrium when the resin in the mold undergoes thermal expansion during temperature ramps. However, once the resin gels, it loses the ability to flow, and supply pressure can no longer be used to influence cavity pressure. Post-gelation, the amount of resin in the mold cavity is fixed, and pressure changes become entirely dependent on density changes. While the total cure shrinkage of this resin is relatively low compared to most epoxies (~1%) [10], it is sufficient to eventually cause the mold cavity pressure to reverse and for a tensile stress state to develop.

Volatile-induced surface porosity occurs due to the combined effects of shrinkage-induced pressure

drops and high resin volatility at low viscosities [8,9]. In the presence of thermal gradients, the cure in the coldest regions of the mold cavity lags behind that of the hotter regions. If the mismatch in cure rate is large enough, the cumulative cure shrinkage of the part becomes enough to cause a pressure drop while the cold zones are still at low viscosity, resulting in the nucleation and growth of voids.

The molding tool used in this study creates temperature gradients primarily in the through-thickness direction (due to having heaters only on one side), and consequently, surface porosity forms exclusively on the colder side. Even though the pressure drop is assumed to extend through the entire thickness of the part, volatile release occurs preferentially in the region of lowest viscosity, and thus porosity forms only on the colder surface. Figure 1 shows an extreme case of cold-side surface porosity, along with hot-side and cross-section views, to illustrate the distribution of this type of defect.

Figure 1: Cold-side, hot-side, and cross-section views of an extreme case of surface porosity.

1.2 Objectives

The present study is part of a larger ongoing research project, the overall goals of which are first, to understand the causes of surface porosity in RTM with this class of resin, and second, to develop guidelines for eliminating this type of defect. The project has involved a combination of both material and process optimization. In total, 5 formulations (each with a different catalyst loading) have been investigated, and over 50 molded samples have been fabricated. The goal of this paper is to present the main findings of the project by discussing the factors that most strongly influence surface porosity. We highlight the results of material optimization by comparing the two formulations with the highest and lowest tendency for porosity formation, using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), rheological dynamic analysis (RDA), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Then, we demonstrate the results of process optimization by comparing the surface quality and data acquired during fabrication of molded samples for the best- and worst-case cure temperature cycles.

Altogether, the results describe the behavior and underlying causes of volatile-induced surface porosity. First, a correlation between increased catalyst loading and decreased volatility is illustrated. Then, the effectiveness of using a 2-stage cure cycle to prevent surface porosity is demonstrated, and explained in terms of the resin density and viscosity histories throughout cure.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

The resin under consideration is a prototype blended formulation that contains both benzoxazine and epoxy constituents, currently under development for the RTM of primary aerospace structures. The benzoxazine component imparts excellent resistance to moisture uptake and chemically aggressive environments, as well as enhanced flammability, smoke, and toxicity (FST) properties. The epoxy component toughens the otherwise brittle benzoxazine matrix, and increases the T_g by raising the maximum theoretical cross-link density [11]. The various formulations used contain the same base materials, but differ in the amount of catalyst included. Presented here are two extreme cases: a low-catalyst version containing 0.1% by weight, and a high-catalyst version containing 2.0%.

All molded samples were reinforced with a quasi-isotropic layup containing 8 layers of five-harness satin (5HS) carbon fiber fabric (364 g/m² areal weight, 3000 fiber/tow count, Sigmatech Ltd.).

2.2 Thermal characterization

The heat of reaction, viscosity, and mass loss behaviour were measured for both formulations by DSC (Q2000, TA Instruments), RDA (AR2000ex, TA Instruments), and TGA (Q5000IR, TA Instruments), respectively. The temperature cycles for all tests consisted of linear ramps from room temperature to 315°C, at rates of 1, 2, and 3°C/min. DSC samples weighed 5 – 10 mg and were loaded in hermetically sealed aluminum pans. RDA tests were performed using disposable aluminum parallel-plate fixtures with a 500 µm gap, in oscillatory mode at 5 Hz. The procedure initially used strain-control-mode at 0.1%, and a cross-over condition was set when the complex viscosity $|\eta^*| > 1000$ Pa·s, at which point the rheometer switched to torque-control-mode at 500 µN·m, to prevent exceeding the instrument's torque limit. TGA tests were performed under atmospheric pressure (with 50 ml/min N₂ purge gas) on samples weighing 40 ± 5 mg.

2.3 RTM manufacturing trials

Carbon fiber reinforced molded samples were fabricated using a lab-scale RTM tool, shown in Figure 2. The main tool body is an anodized aluminum block that contains heating elements, resin inlet/outlet ports, thermocouples, and a pressure sensor. A “picture frame” spacer plate determines the thickness (3.2 mm) and in-plane dimensions (76 × 127 mm) of the mold cavity, and a 20 mm thick tempered glass plate acts as the second tool-face.

Figure 2: Front view and exploded view CAD render of the lab-scale RTM.

The transparent window into the mold cavity is a distinguishing feature of this tool, and allows *in situ* observations of injection and cure. A portable USB microscope was used to record time-lapse videos of the laminate surface during cure, to enable accurate determination of the timing of porosity formation.

Resin was vacuum-degassed for 45 minutes at 80°C and immediately loaded into a pneumatic injector (Radius 2100cc). Injections were performed at 110°C and a positive pressure of 300 kPa, with vacuum being applied to the mold cavity both before and during injection. Excess resin was flushed through the outlet until no bubbles were visible in the tubing or in the mold cavity, as observed through the window. Injection was completed by closing the outlet valve, leaving the inlet valve open, and applying a hydrostatic pressure of 450 kPa using the regulator on the injector's compressed air supply.

The baseline cure cycle consisted of a 2°C/min ramp from the injection temperature (110°C) to the nominal cure temperature of 185°C, followed by a 90 minute dwell. A modified 2-stage cure cycle, which resulted in minimal surface porosity, included an intermediate dwell for 180 minutes at 130°C.

After de-molding, the surface quality was evaluated by measuring the percent defective area. High-resolution photographs were converted to binary maps of void distribution using an open-source image processing software (ImageJ v1.48). Due to the configuration of the molding tool (with heating elements on only one side of the sample), the window-side was always cooler than the tool-side, and consequently, surface porosity appeared exclusively on the window-side of molded samples. Thus, only the window-side was considered when evaluating the surface quality.

3 MATERIAL OPTIMIZATION

Figure 3 shows DSC, RDA, and TGA data for resin cured under linear temperature ramps at 1, 2, and 3°C/min. Two resin formulations are compared, which contain 0.1% and 2.0% by weight of catalyst. The low-catalyst formulation represents the worst-case scenario, with all molded samples exhibiting >10% defective surface area (see Figure 1), while the high-catalyst formulation resulted in surfaces with porosity levels between 4% and < 0.1%.

The degree of cure (α), computed using a normalized running integral of the cure exotherm as measured by DSC, is shown on the top graph. The main difference between the resins is that the onset of cure occurs at lower temperatures for the high-catalyst formulation. The absolute magnitude of the complex viscosity, $|\eta^*|$, is shown on the middle graph. Because the high-catalyst formulation starts to cure at lower temperatures, the onset of gelation also occurs earlier than for the low-catalyst formulation. The bottom graph shows the rate of mass loss, caused by the evaporation of volatiles initially dissolved in the resin. Both formulations behave similarly at lower temperatures, the rate of mass loss having an approximately exponential temperature dependence. In all cases the rate of mass loss eventually decreases to zero, which can be attributed to the increasing viscosity of the resin. The initial deviation from the exponentially increasing mass loss rate roughly corresponds to the onset of gelation, and the ultimate cessation of volatile release is assumed to be caused by a threshold mechanical state, at which point the resin has solidified and evaporation can no longer occur. Markers on each curve denote where the mass loss fell below a threshold rate, and vertical arrows point to the corresponding points on the graphs above. The “critical viscosity” and “critical degree of cure” ranges, corresponding to the threshold state that inhibits mass loss, are indicated by horizontal bands.

The area under each mass loss rate curve represents the total mass loss for that test. All high-catalyst tests lost 5-6% of the initial mass, while the low-catalyst tests lost 11-13%. Because the high-catalyst resin gels at lower temperatures, mass loss is inhibited earlier. Not only is the time window in which mass loss can occur shorter, but by reaching the “critical” state at lower temperatures, the rate of mass loss never reaches the same high values that the low-catalyst formulation exhibits. Furthermore, because the driving force for volatilization is weaker at lower temperatures, the “critical” state occurs at lower α and $|\eta^*|$ values for the high-catalyst formulation. This is noteworthy because, to prevent porosity formation, the critical state must be reached before the pressure drop occurs.

In short, higher catalyst concentrations decrease the potential for volatile release because gelation occurs faster, and before high temperatures are reached. Attaining a “critical” α of 0.35 (for the high-catalyst resin) before the pressure drop is much more feasible than a value of 0.75 (for the low-catalyst

resin), since cure shrinkage (generally assumed to progress linearly with α [12]) will have progressed more than twice as much in the latter case before a “safe” viscosity is reached.

Figure 3: Degree of cure, complex viscosity, and mass loss rate as measured by DSC, RDA, and TGA (respectively). Formulations with 0.1% and 2.0% catalyst are shown, cured under ambient pressure with linear temperature ramps at 1, 2, and 3°C/minute. Vertical lines indicate the moments when mass loss passed below a threshold value, and horizontal bands indicate the degree of cure and viscosity values corresponding to those times.

There is, of course, a limit to how much catalyst can be used. Excessively catalyzed formulations can have severely reduced pot-life, limiting the possible injection time and thus the size of parts that can be produced (or, limiting the number of parts per batch, in the case of an injection system loaded for multiple shots). Additionally, the catalyst has a slight detrimental effect on the resin’s maximum service temperature. The benzoxazine monomers can undergo ring-opening polymerization by two mechanisms, forming either a phenolic-type or a phenoxy-type structure [13]. The phenolic-type contains a pendant hydroxyl group, with which the epoxy monomers react to form cross-links between the benzoxazine main chains. The catalyst promotes the phenoxy-type reaction, however, which reduces the cross-link density and consequently lowers the T_g (from 202°C for the 0.1% catalyst formulation to 188°C for the 2.0% formulation). Of the resins tested for this project, the 2.0% catalyst formulation is considered preferable, having enough catalyst to prevent surface porosity while retaining acceptable pot

life (~4 hours at 110°C) and T_g . A more comprehensive comparison of these resin formulations is given in a companion paper [14].

4. PROCESS OPTIMIZATION

The results of process optimization efforts are exemplified here by a comparison of two samples, which exhibit behavior representative of the trends and phenomena seen in all manufacturing trials with these resins. Figure 4 shows measured temperature (A) and pressure (B) data for molded samples fabricated with the 2.0% catalyst formulation, using the two cure cycles that resulted in the highest and lowest surface porosity levels. Additionally, viscosity envelopes (C) are shown for the two cycles, which assume for the cold-side a 3% temperature lag (relative to room temperature) and a 4 minute time lag (based on previous measurements from thermocouples embedded in both sides of molded samples [8]). The “safe” zone, where viscosity exceeds the critical value needed to prevent volatile release, is shown shaded in green. The critical value of 2×10^4 Pa·s corresponds to the top of the blue horizontal band on the viscosity graph in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Temperature (A), pressure (B), and viscosity (C) graphs for the 2.0% catalyst formulation cured using the baseline and a 2-stage cycle. Dotted vertical lines indicate the times when pressure fell below the critical value. Binary maps of surfaces are shown on the right.

Both cure cycles began with injection at 110°C, corresponding to $t = 10 - 13$ minutes on Figure 4. For the baseline cycle, starting at $t = 16$ minutes, the temperature was increased at 2°C/min to 185°C and held for 90 minutes. The 2-stage cure cycle differed only by the addition of a 180-minute dwell at 130°C. For the baseline cure cycle, the cavity pressure rose slightly above the supply level due to resin thermal expansion during the temperature ramp, but soon after gelation, the pressure dropped below the critical value required to suppress volatile release (indicated by a vertical dotted line at $t = 55$ min). The viscosity envelope for the baseline cure cycle shows rapid gelation – the viscosity increasing from < 1 Pa·s to $> 2 \times 10^4$ Pa·s in under 10 minutes – creating an order-of-magnitude viscosity gradient though the thickness of the part at the time of the pressure drop. The time between when the pressure drop occurred and when the cold-side viscosity reached the “safe” zone, from $t = 55 - 58$ min, corresponds precisely to when surface voids were observed to nucleate and grow rapidly (a binary map of the cold-side surface is shown on the right).

Conversely, the viscosity envelope for the case of the 2-stage cure cycle was entirely in the “safe” zone at the time of the pressure drop, and only minor surface porosity formed. The difference is, in part, due to the limited reaction rate at 130°C, which reduces the through-thickness viscosity gradient. An additional feature of the 2-stage cycle that aids in suppressing surface porosity can be seen in the cavity pressure behavior between the beginning of the final temperature ramp at $t = 206$ minutes and the time of the pressure drop at $t = 232$ minutes. Toward the end of the 130°C dwell, the cavity pressure had already begun to deviate from the supply level, indicating that the resin had gelled and was increasing in density (or, equivalently, decreasing in specific volume). The pressure would have soon dropped below the critical value, but the temperature ramp caused thermal expansion of the resin (see Figure 5), temporarily increasing the pressure until cure shrinkage finally progressed enough to cause an abrupt pressure drop. The additional time afforded by using thermal expansion to partially counteract cure shrinkage (and the increased reaction rate at higher temperatures) allowed the viscosity envelope to reach sufficiently high values such that only minimal surface porosity formed.

Figure 5: A schematic representation of density changes for the two cure cycles from Figure 4, including the experimentally determined pressure drops.

Figure 5 shows a schematic representation of density changes during processing, assuming linear dependencies on both temperature and degree of cure, relative to a reference state A (room temperature, $\alpha = 0$). Point B corresponds to injection, after which the baseline cycle ramps to 185°C, dwells there until point E, and then cools back to room temperature (point F). The gel-point is indicated at $\alpha = 0.15$, which corresponds to the degree of cure at the onset of gelation from the data in Figure 3 (for the high-catalyst formulation). Upon gelation, the amount of resin in the mold cavity becomes fixed, and a density increase of ~0.2% results in a loss of cavity pressure. The 2-stage cure cycle, however, reaches the gel-point during the 130°C hold between points C and D. At point D, if cure shrinkage were to continue, a pressure drop would occur. By instead ramping upwards in temperature at this point, the density briefly decreases. By moving roughly parallel to the iso- ρ contours, we can temporarily increase α without increasing density, and consequently, α reaches a higher value at the time of the pressure drop compared to the baseline cure cycle.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have shown how, in the RTM processing of a resin with increased volatility, rapid curing and thermal gradients can lead to the formation of surface porosity on the cold side of molded parts. Furthermore, we have shown that the severity of this phenomenon can vary dramatically, from $\gg 10\%$ defective area (see Figure 1) to ~0.1% defective area (see Figure 4), solely by modifying the cure kinetics via catalyst concentration and imposed cure temperature cycle. Increased catalyst loadings reduce the tendency for volatile release by gelling at lower temperatures, and a 2-stage cure cycle prevents porosity formation by reducing the hot-side/cold-side viscosity gradient and by leveraging thermal expansion to partially counteract cure shrinkage. The capacity to manufacture parts with defect-free surface finishes justifies the use of RTM, which can reduce costly and time-consuming post-cure finishing steps, thereby improving manufacturing efficiency.

In a broader context, this type of analysis could be expanded to other resin systems that display similar behavior. The direct *in situ* observational capabilities enabled through the use of an RTM with a transparent tool plate can provide insight into many in-mold phenomena, contrary to the usual “black box” nature of RTM processing. Next-generation blended resins often involve overlapping and competing reactions, whose complexities dictate the need for careful observations, analysis, and insights into their behavior. To address this need, the tools and approach illustrated here may aid in the development of new blended resins that overcome the limitations of single-resin formulations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge financial and material support from the M.C. Gill Composites Center. Undergraduate research assistant Matthew Thomas contributed to the experimental characterization of the resin.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kruckenberg, T. and Paton, R., *Resin Transfer Moulding for Aerospace Structures*, Springer Netherlands, 1998, ([doi: 10.1007/978-94-011-4437-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-4437-7)).
- [2] Pearce, N., Guild, F. and Summerscales, J., A study of the effects of convergent flow fronts on the properties of fibre reinforced composites produced by RTM, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 1998, pp. 141–52, ([doi: 10.1016/S1359-835X\(97\)00041-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(97)00041-9)).
- [3] Ruiz, E., Achim, V., Soukane, S., Trochu, F. and Bréard, J. (2006) Optimization of injection flow rate to minimize micro/macro-voids formation in resin transfer molded composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 475–86, ([doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.06.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.06.013)).

- [4] Liu, B., Bickerton, S. and Advani, S.G., Modelling and simulation of resin transfer moulding (RTM) - Gate control, venting and dry spot prediction, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **27**, 1996, pp. 135–41, ([doi: 10.1016/1359-835X\(95\)00012-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/1359-835X(95)00012-Q)).
- [5] Lo, J., Anders, M., Centea, T. and Nutt, S.R., Characterizing Volatile Release In An RTM Resin via Dielectric Cure Monitoring, FTIR, TGA, and DSC, *Proceedings of SAMPE Tech 2014, Seattle WA, USA*.
- [6] Lundström, T.S., Measurement of void collapse during resin transfer moulding, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 1997, pp. 201–14, ([doi: 10.1016/S1359-835X\(96\)00109-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(96)00109-1)).
- [7] Eom, Y., Boogh, L., Michaud, V., Sunderland, P. and Månson, J.A., Stress-initiated void formation during cure of a three-dimensionally constrained thermoset resin, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **41**, 2001, pp. 492–503, ([doi: 10.1002/pen.10746](https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.10746)).
- [8] Anders, M., Lo, J., Centea, T. and Nutt, S., Volatile-Induced Voids In RTM Processing For Aerospace, *12th International Conference on Flow Processes in Composite Materials, Enschede, NL, 2014*.
- [9] Anders, M., Lo, J., Centea, T. and Nutt, S., Eliminating Volatile-Induced Surface Porosity for the Resin Transfer Molding of a Benzoxazine/Epoxy Blend, *Unpublished Manuscript*, 2015.
- [10] Centea, T., Lo, J., Anders, M. and Nutt, S.R., Process Modeling for Resin Transfer Molding of a Modified Heterocyclic Phenolic/Epoxy Blended Resin, *Proceedings of the 29th ASC Technical Conference, La Jolla, CA, USA, 2014*.
- [11] Ishida, H. and Allen, D.J., Mechanical characterization of copolymers based on benzoxazine and epoxy, *Polymer*, **37**, 1996, pp. 4487–95, ([doi: 10.1016/0032-3861\(96\)00303-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861(96)00303-5)).
- [12] Nawab, Y., Shahid, S., Boyard, N. and Jacquemin, F., Chemical shrinkage characterization techniques for thermoset resins and associated composites, *Journal of Materials Science*, **48**, 2013, pp. 5387–409, ([doi: 10.1007/s10853-013-7333-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-013-7333-6)).
- [13] Ghosh, N.N., Kiskan, B. and Yagci, Y., Polybenzoxazines—New high performance thermosetting resins: Synthesis and properties, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **32**, 2007, pp. 1344–91, ([doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2007.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2007.07.002)).
- [14] Lo, J., Anders, M., Centea, T. and Nutt, S., Multi-Scale Material And Process Characterization for Resin Transfer Molding: Case Study for a Blended Epoxy/Phenolic Resin, *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2015*.